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IOT SECURITY: PENETRATION TESTING OF WHITE-LABEL CLOUD-BASED IOT CAMERA COMPROMISING PERSONAL DATA PRIVACY

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ABSTRACT

The Internet is driving force on how we communicate with one another, from posting messages and images to Facebook or “tweeting” your activities from your vacation. Today it is being used everywhere, now imagine a device that connects to the internet sends out data based on its sensors, this is the Internet-ofThings, a connection of objects with a plethora of sensors. Smart devices as they are commonly called, are invading our homes. With the proliferation of cheap Cloud-based IoT Camera use as a surveillance system to monitor our homes and loved ones right from the palm of our hand using our smartphones. These cameras are mostly white-label product, a process in which the product comes from a single manufacturer and bought by a different company where they are re-branded and sold with their own product name, a method commonly practice in the retail and manufacturing industry. Each Cloud-based IoT cameras sold are not properly tested for security. The problem arises when a hacker, hacks into the Cloud-based IoT Camera sees everything we do, without us knowing about it. Invading our personal digital privacy. This study focuses on the vulnerabilities found on White-label Cloud-based IoT Camera on the market specifically on a Chinese brand sold by Shenzhen Gwelltimes Technology. How this IoT device can be compromised and how to protect our selves from such cyber-attacks.

KEYWORDS

Network Protocols, Wireless Network, Mobile Network, Virus, Worms & Trojon, Internet of Things, Hacker, Smart Camera.

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LIDAR POINT CLOUD CLASSIFICATION USING EXPECTATION MAXIMIZATION ALGORITHM

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ABSTRACT

EM algorithm is a common algorithm in data mining techniques. With the idea of using two iterations of E and M, the algorithm creates a model that can assign class labels to data points. In addition, EM not only optimizes the parameters of the model but also can predict device data during the iteration. Therefore, the paper focuses on researching and improving the EM algorithm to suit the LiDAR point cloud classification. Based on the idea of breaking point cloud and using the scheduling parameter for step E to help the algorithm converge faster with a shorter run time. The proposed algorithm is tested with measurement data set in Nghe An province, Vietnam for more than 92% accuracy and has faster runtime than the original EM algorithm.

KEYWORDS

LiDAR, EM algorithm, Scheduling parameter, LiDAR point elevation, GMM model

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WEB SERVICES AS A SOLUTION FOR CLOUD ENTERPRISE RESOURCE PLANNING INTEROPERABILITY

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ABSTRACT

Recently, organizations have shown more interest in cloud computing because of the many advantages they provide (cost savings, storage capacity, scalability, and speed of loading). Enterprise resource planning (ERP) systems are one of the most important systems that have been upgraded to cloud computing. In this thesis, we focus on cloud ERP interoperability, which is an important challenge in cloud ERP. Interoperability is the ability of different components to work in independent clouds with no or minimum user effort. More than 20% of the risk rate of cloud adoption is caused by interoperability. Thus, we propose web services as a solution for cloud ERP interoperability. The proposed solution increases interoperability between different cloud service providers and between cloud ERP systems with other applications in a company.

KEYWORDS

Cloud computing, ERP, interoperability, web services

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BIG DATA IN CLOUD COMPUTING REVIEW AND OPPORTUNITIES

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ABSTRACT

Big Data is used in decision making process to gain useful insights hidden in the data for business and engineering. At the same time it presents challenges in processing, cloud computing has helped in advancement of big data by providing computational, networking and storage capacity. This paper presents the review, opportunities and challenges of transforming big data using cloud computing resources.

KEYWORDS

Big data; cloud computing; analytics; database; data warehouse

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SMART MOTORCYCLE HELMET: REAL-TIME CRASH DETECTION WITH EMERGENCY NOTIFICATION, TRACKER AND ANTI-THEFT SYSTEM USING INTERNET-OF-THINGS CLOUD BASED TECHNOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

Buying a car entails a cost, not counting the day to day high price tag of gasoline. People are looking for viable means of transportation that is cost-effective and can move its way through traffic faster. In the Philippines, motorcycle was the answer to most people transportation needs. With the increasing number of a motorcycle rider in the Philippines safety is the utmost concern. Today technology plays a huge role on how this safety can be assured. We now see advances in connected devices. Devices can sense its surrounding through sensor attach to it. With this in mind, this study focuses on the development of a wearable device named Smart Motorcycle Helmet or simply Smart Helmet, whose main objective is to help motorcycle rider in times of emergency. Utilizing sensors such as alcohol level detector, crash/impact sensor, Internet connection thru 3G, accelerometer, Short Message Service (SMS) and cloud computing infrastructure connected to a Raspberry Pi Zero-W and integrating a separate Arduino board for the anti-theft tracking module is used to develop the propose Internet-of Things (IoT) device.

Using quantitative method and descriptive type research, the researchers validated the results from the inputs of the participant who tested the smart helmet during the alpha and beta testing process. Taking into account the ethical consideration of the volunteers, who will test the Smart Helmet. To ensure the reliability of the beta and alpha testing, ISO 25010 quality model was used for the assessment focusing on the device accuracy, efficiency and functionality. Based on the inputs and results gathered, the proposed Smart Helmet IoT device can be used as a tool in helping a motorcycle rider when an accident happens to inform the first-responder of the accident location and informing the family of the motorcycle rider.

KEYWORDS

Smart Helmet, Internet of Things, Sensors, Real-Time Crash Detection, Emergency Notification, Tracker, Anti-Theft System Cloud Based Technology

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A SURVEY ON SECURITY CHALLENGES OF VIRTUALIZATION TECHNOLOGY IN CLOUD COMPUTING

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ABSTRACT

Virtualization has become a widely and attractive employed technology in cloud computing environments. Sharing of a single physical machine between multiple isolated virtual machines leading to a more optimized hardware usage, as well as make the migration and management of a virtual system more efficiently than its physical counterpart. Virtualization is a fundamental technology in a cloud environment. However, the presence of an additional abstraction layer among software and hardware causes new security issues. Security issues related to virtualization technology have become a significant concern for organizations due to arising some new security challenges.

This paper aims to identify the main challenges and risks of virtualization in cloud computing environments. Furthermore, it focuses on some common virtual-related threats and attacks affect the security of cloud computing.

The survey was conducted to obtain the views of the cloud stakeholders on virtualization vulnerabilities, threats, and approaches that can be used to overcome them.

Finally, we propose recommendations for improving security, and mitigating risks encounter virtualization that necessary to adopt secure cloud computing.

KEYWORDS

Cloud Computing, Virtualization, Security, Challenge, Risk

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GROUP BASED RESOURCE MANAGEMENT AND PRICING MODEL IN CLOUD COMPUTING

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ABSTRACT

Cloud computing utilizes large scale computing infrastructure that has been radically changing the IT landscape enabling remote access to computing resources with low service cost, high scalability , availability and accessibility. Serving tasks from multiple users where the tasks are of different characteristics with variation in the requirement of computing power may cause under or over utilization of resources. Therefore maintaining such mega-scale datacenter requires efficient resource management procedure to increase resource utilization. However, while maintaining efficiency in service provisioning it is necessary to ensure the maximization of profit for the cloud providers. Most of the current research works aims at how providers can offer efficient service provisioning to the user and improving system performance. There are comparatively fewer specific works regarding resource management which also deals with the economic section that considers profit maximization for the provider. In this paper we represent a model that deals with both efficient resource utilization and pricing of the resources. The joint resource management model combines the work of user assignment, task scheduling and load balancing on the fact of CPU power endorsement. We propose four algorithms respectively for user assignment, task scheduling, load balancing and pricing that works on group based resources offering reduction in task execution time(56.3%),activated physical machines(41.44%),provisioning cost(23%) . The cost is calculated over a time interval involving the number of served customer at this time and the amount of resources used within this time.

KEYWORDS

Resource Management, Resource Pricing, Task Execution, Load Balancing, Task Scheduling.

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A NEW CONTEXT-SENSITIVE DECISION MAKING SYSTEM FOR MOBILE CLOUD OFFLOADING

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ABSTRACT

Recently, with the rapid spread use of mobile devices, some problems have begun to emerge. The most important of these are that the mobile devices batteries' life may be short and that these devices may be in some cases. The complex tasks that must be addressed to solve such problems on mobile devices can be transferred to the cloud environment when appropriate conditions are met. The decision to offload to the cloud environment at this stage is very important. In this thesis, a context-aware decision-making system has been developed for offloading to cloud environments. Unlike similar tasks, the processes determined for transfer to the cloud are not run randomly, but rather according to the mobile user's application usage habits. The developed system was implemented in a real environment for one month. According to the results, it was determined that processes transferred to the cloud were completed in less time and consumed less energy.

KEYWORDS

Mobile Cloud Offloading, Mobile Cloud Computing, Context-Aware System, Forecasting, Dynamic Estimation, Energy-Efficiency

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DISTRIBUTED SCHEME TO AUTHENTICATE DATA STORAGE SECURITY IN CLOUD COMPUTING

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ABSTRACT

Cloud Computing is the revolution in current generation IT enterprise. Cloud computing displaces database and application software to the large data centres, where the management of services and data may not be predictable, where as the conventional solutions, for IT services are under proper logical, physical and personal controls. This aspect attribute, however comprises different security challenges which have not been well understood. It concentrates on cloud data storage security which has always been an important aspect of quality of service (QOS). In this paper, we designed and simulated an adaptable and efficient scheme to guarantee the correctness of user data stored in the cloud and also with some prominent features. Homomorphic token is used for distributed verification of erasure – coded data. By using this scheme, we can identify misbehaving servers. In spite of past works, our scheme supports effective and secure dynamic operations on data blocks such as data insertion, deletion and modification. In contrast to traditional solutions, where the IT services are under proper physical, logical and personnel controls, cloud computing moves the application software and databases to the large data centres, where the data management and services may not be absolutely truthful. This effective security and performance analysis describes that the proposed scheme is extremely flexible against malicious data modification, convoluted failures and server clouding attacks.

KEYWORDS

Cloud Computing, Cloud Storage Security, Homomorphic token, EC2, S3

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MULTILEVEL ANALYSIS OF STUDENT'S FEEDBACK USING MOODLE LOGS IN VIRTUAL CLOUD ENVIRONMENT

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ABSTRACT

In the current digital era, education system has witness tremendous growth in data storage and efficient retrieval. Many Institutes have very huge databases which may be of terabytes of knowledge and information. The complexity of the data is an important issue as educational data consists of structural as well as non-structural type which includes various text editors like node pad, word, PDF files, images, video, etc. The problem lies in proper storage and correct retrieval of this information. Different types of learning platform like Moodle have implemented to integrate the requirement of educators, administrators and learner. Although this type of platforms are indeed a great support of educators, still mining of the large data is required to uncover various interesting patterns and facts for decision making process for the benefits of the students. In this research work, different data mining classification models are applied to analyse and predict students' feedback based on their Moodle usage data. The models described in this paper surely assist the educators, decision maker, mentors to early engage with the issues as address by students. In this research, real data from a semester has been experimented and evaluated. To achieve the better classification models, discretization and weight adjustment techniques have also been applied as part of the pre – processing steps. Finally, we conclude that for efficient decision making with the student's feedback the classifier model must be appropriate in terms of accuracy and other important evaluation measures. Our experiments also shows that by using weight adjustment techniques like information gain and support vector machines improves the performance of classification models.

KEYWORDS

Educational Data, Educational Data Mining, LMS, Moodle, Feedback system, weight adjustment techniques.

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